

On the Application of e^{hD^2} to Evaluate Integrals

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Abstract— We derive some results on determining the exponential of a derivative squared and apply it to several integrals including a communication theory integral. Using this technique, one can, in principle, compute the expected value of any function whose variables are Gaussian distributed. Some generalizations to defining functions defined as operators acting on other functions is also briefly considered.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The Taylor series expansion of an exponential function can be written as

$$e^{ax} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{a^m}{m!} x^m \quad (1)$$

which can also be viewed as a formal series [6]. If we replace x by $D = \frac{d}{dt}$, then (1) makes sense provided e^{aD} is assumed to be operating on a

function. Thus, one has the interpretation

$$e^{\pm aD} f(x) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{a^m}{m!} (\pm 1)^m (D^m f(x)) \quad (2)$$

Note, by Taylor's theorem, we have the identity

$$e^{zD} u(t) = u(t+z) \quad (3)$$

It follows from this property that e^{zD} is a *natural operator* [5]. It turns out that the only linear natural operator series is the exponential e^{azD} or linear combinations thereof. Some non-linear operators are also natural. It is natural to consider higher powers of D in the exponential to determine whether they have any useful simple representation. It turns out that they do, which we discovered when considering a particular integral.

The integral

$$G(a, b) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-a^2(u-b)^2} \operatorname{erf}(u) du \quad (4)$$

arose in a probability application where

$$\operatorname{erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x e^{-\frac{q^2}{2}} dq \quad (5)$$

is the error function. We would like to determine a rapidly convergent form for Eq. (5) if possible. In the original attempt to evaluate this integral, we were lead to a representation of the form

$$G \cong \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-a)^m}{m!} \frac{d^{2m}}{dp^{2m}} \left(\frac{1}{p} e^{\frac{p^2}{4}} \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{p}{2}\right) \right) \quad (6)$$

Note that this formula comes from considering the integral as the Laplace transform of the error function and expanding the Gaussian function as a Taylor series. While this particular form did not lead to a useful result, consideration of e^{aD^2} ($D = \frac{d}{dp}$) did.

The operator e^{aD^2} arises in some applications as mentioned earlier. It turns out that there is a useful representation for this operator. The operator can be represented by the integral [3]

$$e^{hD^2} f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-y^2} f(2\sqrt{h}y + x) dy \quad (7)$$

or equivalently

$$e^{hD^2} f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{4h\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{(u-x)^2}{4h}} f(u) du \quad (8)$$

This result can be justified by a heuristic Fourier analysis proof as is done in the Appendix A. The alternative form is equivalent to taking the expected value of a random variable $f(u)$ assuming that the probability distribution is Gaussian. Three specific examples of this transform are discussed that are of some interest. Certain integrals arise in communication theory [4] that

are also useful as models of probability density functions. We originally transformed this integral into a series that resemble the Rodrigues' formula expansion of an orthogonal polynomial. An alternative representation of this integral lead to functions of derivatives operating on a function. This leads to some interesting questions on the representations of operators which will not be considered here. We now consider three specific applications.

Example 1 BALLISTIC

ESTIMATOR APPLICATION: *In trying to determine good estimators for the ballistic coefficient, β , one arrives at a formula that requires knowing the expected value of the logarithm of a random variable that is normally distributed. Determining the expected value of the logarithm is problematic. An approximate expression can be obtained assuming the noise distribution of the probability density function is Gaussian. The integral to be evaluated*

$$I = E[\ln(V)] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_v^2}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \ln(V) \exp\left(-\frac{(V-V_0)^2}{2\sigma_v^2}\right)$$

is recognized as the Weierstrass transform of the logarithm with $x = V_0$ and $h = \frac{\sigma_v^2}{2}$ assuming that the expression for the derivatives is interpreted as a formal series. The resultant formal series

$$\ln(V_0) - \frac{\sigma_v}{\sqrt{2}V_0^2} - \frac{3\sigma_v^2}{V_0^4} - \dots - \frac{(2n-1)!\sigma_v^n}{2^{\frac{n}{2}}V_0^{2n}} - \dots$$

is clearly convergent with only the first few terms mattering and

$$I = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_v^2}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \ln(V) \exp\left(-\frac{(V-V_0)^2}{2\sigma_v^2}\right) dV \\ \cong \ln(V_0) - \frac{\sigma_v}{\sqrt{2}V_0^2}$$

which appears to a reasonably good approximation of what is happening, provided the variance

is small compared to the velocity squared. This approach is an object lesson on how to use informal mathematics to obtain practical results.

Example 2 RYDBERG ATOM¹: An application that occurs in optics to calculate the spectrum of an atom that is radiating according to a certain spectral function. A particular form that is of interest is to evaluate

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-y^2}}{(u-y)^2 + a^2} dy$$

which is recognized as the same form as Eq. (8) with $a^2 = \frac{1}{4h}$, $x = -\frac{u}{a}$, and $f(x) = \frac{1}{x^2+1}$. Thus

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-y^2}}{(u-y)^2 + a^2} dy = \frac{1}{a^2\sqrt{\pi}} e^{hD^2} \left(\frac{1}{x^2+1} \right)$$

which is rapidly convergent for $a < \frac{1}{2}$. For larger a , a different scaling method is preferable.

II. APPLICATION TO A COMMUNICATION THEORY INTEGRALS

Certain integrals arise in communication theory [4] that are also useful as models of probability density functions. We originally transformed this integral into a series that resemble the Rodrigues' formula expansion of an orthogonal polynomial. An alternative representation of this integral lead to functions of derivatives operating on a function. First, note the integral in (7) can be rewritten as

$$I(h, x) = \frac{1}{a} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-y^2} \operatorname{erf}(2\sqrt{h}y + x) dy, \quad (9)$$

where $y = a(u-b)$, $x = b$, and $2\sqrt{h} = \frac{1}{a}$. By (7), this becomes

$$I(h, x) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{a} e^{hD^2} \operatorname{erf}(x) \quad (10)$$

¹This application is due to Dan Parks (NSWCDD, Division B10) where it arose in a quantum mechanics application.

Now, from [1]

$$\frac{d^{n+1}}{dz^{n+1}} \operatorname{erf}(z) = (-1)^n \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} H_n(z) e^{-z^2} \quad (11)$$

where $H_n(z)$ is the n -th Hermite polynomial. Substituting (11) into (10) gives the final result

$$I(h, x) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{a} \operatorname{erf}(x) - \frac{2}{a} \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{h^m}{m!} H_{2m-1}(x) \right) e^{-x^2} \quad (12)$$

This has given an improvement in terms of speed of computation over conventional numerical integration. Note for $a > .5$, the rapid convergence of (12) breaks down, even though the series has an infinite radius of convergence.

An alternative method, that seems to have the rapid convergence property, is to rewrite (9) as

$$I(a, b) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-a^2w^2} \operatorname{erf}(w+b) dw \quad (13)$$

Then using the expansion in (3) of the integral gives

$$I(a, b) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-a^2w^2} \operatorname{erf}(w) dw + \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{b^n}{n!} (-1)^n \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-(a^2+1)w^2} H_{n-1}(w) dw \quad (14)$$

Note that the first integral is zero since $\operatorname{erf}(x)$ is an odd function, while the second is zero for odd n . Let $\gamma = \sqrt{a^2+1}$, so that $I(a, b)$ can be written as

$$I(\gamma, b) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{b^{2m}}{(2m)!} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\gamma^2w^2} H_{2m-1}(w) dw \quad (15)$$

which is evaluated in Appendix B. An incomplete form of (9) has been treated by an alternative approach [4]. Define the incomplete form of (15) as

$$I(h, x, v) = \frac{1}{a} \int_v^{\infty} e^{-y^2} \operatorname{erf}(2\sqrt{h}y + x) dy \quad (16)$$

while the complimentary form is

$$I_*(h, x, v) = \frac{1}{a} \int_{-\infty}^v e^{-y^2} \operatorname{erf}(2\sqrt{h}y + x) dy \quad (17)$$

so that

$$I(h, x, v) + I_*(h, x, v) = I(h, x) \quad (18)$$

The trick is to find a convenient way to compute (17) or (18) that gives a good computational savings. The methods developed here can be used to treat a complete parameter range for a , but this aspect of the problem will be reserved for a paper that treats the problem more completely.

III. DISCUSSION

Since our primary purpose was to educational, namely to show how to evaluate the integrals by a method that is not well known to the applied community, more than a brief discussion of the underlying mathematics is not appropriate here. There are several observations, however, that seem worth pursuing. There is an underlying connection between wavelets and operator series that appears to have gone un-noticed. The integral transform in (7) resembles a Fresnel or Morlet transform for continuous wavelets. The connection between the integral and generalized Taylor series of derivatives is suggestive of some alternative ways of representing data.

Remark 1 *Thanks to Norm Hecht for reading this document and making suggestions that improved the contents.*

I. A

APPENDIX A: PROOF

In this appendix, we derive the formula

$$e^{hD^2} f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-y^2} f(2\sqrt{h}y + x) dy \quad (19)$$

using Fourier integrals. Write the left-hand-side of (19) as $g(x)$, and take the Fourier transform

as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{g}(\omega) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-y^2} f(2\sqrt{h}y + x) e^{j\omega x} dx dy \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-y^2} e^{2\sqrt{h}yD} f(x) e^{j\omega x} dx dy \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dy e^{-y^2} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2\sqrt{h}y)^m}{m!} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f^{(m)}(x) e^{j\omega x} dx \\ &= \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2j\sqrt{h}\omega)^m}{m!} \hat{f}(\omega) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} y^m e^{-y^2} dy \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

To evaluate (20), note that when m is odd, the integral is zero since the integrand is an odd function in y . Let $m = 2n$, and make the change of variables $y^2 = u$; thus final integral becomes a gamma function, so $\hat{g}(\omega)$ becomes

$$\hat{g}(\omega) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-2^2 h \omega^2)^n}{(2n)!} \Gamma(n + \frac{1}{2}) \hat{f}(\omega) \quad (21)$$

Using the duplication formula for the gamma function [2]

$$2^{2z-1} \Gamma(z) \Gamma(z + \frac{1}{2}) = \sqrt{\pi} \Gamma(2z),$$

in the sum so (21) yields

$$\hat{g}(\omega) = \sqrt{\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n h^n \frac{\omega^{2n}}{n!} \hat{f}(\omega) \quad (22)$$

Taking the inverse Fourier transform of (22) and noting $(-1)^n \omega^{2n} \hat{f}(\omega) \Leftrightarrow \frac{d^{2n} f(x)}{dx^{2n}}$, gives

$$g(x) = \sqrt{\pi} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{h^m}{m!} \frac{d^{2m} f(x)}{dx^{2m}} = \sqrt{\pi} e^{hD^2} f(x) \quad (23)$$

which proves the result.

I. A

APPENDIX B: EVALUATION OF INTEGRAL

In this appendix, we evaluate (11)

$$I(m, \gamma) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\gamma^2 w^2} H_{2m-1}(w) dw \quad (24)$$

using the representation for the Hermite polynomials

$$H_n(x) = \sum_{s=0}^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} (-1)^s (2x)^{n-2s} \frac{n!}{s!(n-2s)!} \quad (25)$$

Substituting this into (24) and making the change of variables $w\gamma = \sqrt{q}$ gives

$$I(m, \gamma) = \frac{1}{\gamma} \sum_{s=0}^{m-1} (-1)^s \left(\frac{2}{\gamma}\right)^{2m-2s-1} \frac{(2m-1)!}{(s)!(2m-2s-1)!} \int_0^\infty e^{-q} q^{m-s-1} dq \quad (26)$$

Note the integral is just a gamma function $\Gamma(m-s)$, so the integral in (26) is the double sum

$$I(\gamma, b) = \frac{2}{\gamma^2 \sqrt{\pi}} \sum_{m=1}^\infty \frac{b^{2m}}{(2m)!} \sum_{s=0}^{m-1} (-1)^s \left(\frac{2}{\gamma}\right)^{2m-2s} \frac{(2m-1)!(m-s-1)!}{(s)!(2m-2s-1)!} \quad (27)$$

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